

UZBEKISTAN IS ONE OF THE SAFE COUNTRIES FOR TOURISM**Buron Jumayev**

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Abstract. In this article, the information related to the tourism potential of Uzbekistan is given as an example of safe tourism, the reforms carried out in this field during the years of independence and the prospective plans implemented by the state are detailed, as well as some scientific and practical suggestions are given. raised.

Keywords: tourism in Uzbekistan, security, tourism, world, reliable, service, foreign.

Since the end of the 20th century, the tourism sector has become one of the main components of population income in many developed and developing countries of the world. Even today, the tourism industry is one of the most promising and rapidly developing branches of the service industry.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said about tourism opportunities: “Tourism is one of the promising industries that bring high income to the national economy today. Uzbekistan is a country with great potential in the field of tourism[1]” he said.

Tourism is a broad concept, and today there are many types of it, depending on the reasons for which tourists visit. For example: gastronomic tourism, ecotourism, agrotourism, sports tourism, cultural tourism, pilgrimage tourism, medical tourism, educational tourism, etc.

Equally wide opportunities are being created for all types of tourism in Uzbekistan, and large-scale cooperation with various countries is being carried out in this regard.

Today, there is tourism related to all types of tourism, and this is gastronomic tourism. Therefore, the safety of gastronomic tourism is very important for the safety of tourism. In this regard, representatives of various fields are conducting great scientific work, for example, Russian researchers have developed an artificial intelligence system that can detect various diseases of vegetables and fruits.

This system was developed by a team of researchers from Skoltex and St. Petersburg State University of Aerospace Instrumentation under the leadership of Skoltex Senior Lecturer Andrey Somov. This research group has been working

for a long time to create artificial intelligence systems that can recognize various products, including vegetables and fruits.

The scientists adapted the new research work of the neural networks they developed to an important and at the same time very labor-intensive task - the detection of various defects and diseases that affect the storage of vegetables and fruits after harvesting. Currently, multi- and hyperspectral cameras operating in the infrared part of the spectrum are used to solve these problems.

The researchers found that the same problem can be solved using conventional cameras and two types of neural networks. In particular, scientists were able to adapt the artificial intelligence system to detect two types of defects on the surface of apples - rot and mold.

Further calculations showed that the artificial intelligence system created by the scientists was able to analyze photos of four different varieties of apples, find moldy and rotten fruits and distinguish them from intact fruits with a probability of 98 percent. This makes it possible to use such algorithms to monitor the condition of the crop and timely remove diseased fruits and vegetables that serve as foci for the spread of diseases[2]. The creation of such safe conditions will serve to increase the flow of tourists for any country.

The CNN Travel website announced that Uzbekistan was included in the list of the best countries to visit for tourists from around the world in 2023. To better understand the Silk Road and the importance of Uzbekistan in it, it is necessary to visit Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. Also, the inclusion of Sentob village of Uzbekistan in the list of «Best Tourist Villages» in 2023 by UNWTO has attracted many tourists, this village has been recognized for its commitment to sustainable development with a focus on nature, organic food and eco-mountain tourism. Uzbekistan now offers visa-free access to citizens of 86 countries, ready to impress visitors with its beautiful landscapes and well-preserved architecture. Singapore, Spain, Indonesia, Angola, Korea and a number of other countries were included in the list of the best countries to visit.

It should be noted that Uzbekistan is the only country from Central Asia included in this list[3]. Uzbekistan was recognized as the best safe country for tourists in Central Asia. The republic is included among countries with a low risk level. So, the level of violence in the country is low, terrorist attacks are not recorded, mass riots are very rare, security and emergency services work efficiently, infrastructure meets generally accepted standards. Besides, we have hospitable and noble people.

Currently, we can cite several other safe countries such as Uzbekistan, analysts of “International SOS” recognize Switzerland, Slovenia, Denmark, Norway, Finland, Iceland and the island of Greenland as the safest countries in the world for tourists. Afghanistan, Ukraine, Iraq, Yemen, Libya, Somalia and South Sudan are classified as extremely dangerous[4].

In general, the most important thing for both domestic and foreign tourists is the safety of the destination, so every country should pay special attention to the security system in order to develop tourism. In this regard, the necessary work is being carried out in Uzbekistan.

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